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Judicialisation of Party Primaries in the 2023 Nigerian General Elections: Implications for Internal Party Democracy

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Abstract

The 2023 general elections in Nigeria were hugely litigated, resulting in many court decisions across party lines. The scenario unpacked the sustained role of the Nigerian courts in settling internal party electoral controversies. Yet, this paper examined the causes, dynamics, and implications of this leaning by investigating selected high-profile cases, especially the debates surrounding the All Progressives Congress (APC) primary, which involved a former Senate President, Lawan Ahmed, and the incumbent Senate President, Senator Godswill Akpabio. Using doctrinal legal analysis, judicial rulings, augmented by current literature, are analyzed to show how varying readings of the Electoral Act 2022, political party constitutions, and intra-party nomination processes led to disparate primary election results at both

tribunals and appellate court levels. The study also explicates how increasing dependence on judicial intervention opened up systemic fragility in intra-party democracy, such as confusing candidate nomination processes, contentious disputes, and shrewd cases by contenders. Results reveal that while court oversight provides constitutional checks on party abuse of power, judicial overbearing influence can weaken party independence and electoral stability. The study recommends reforms to improve internal party democracy, clarify statutory provisions, and reassess the balance between judicial review and political self-regulation in Nigeria's electoral system.

Keywords: Judiciary, election, party primaries, internal democracy, Nigeria **SDG 16:** Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions

Introduction

Democratic institutions, especially political parties, act as the foundation for recruiting, selecting, and presenting candidates for elected positions at all levels of government in every democratic system (Ndubuisi & Omerire, 2025). In Nigeria and other political environments, the process of choosing these candidates, particularly through party primaries, plays a key role in determining election results. Therefore, the constitutionality, transparency, and integrity of party primaries are essential for electoral legitimacy. The 2023 Nigerian election, conducted under the Electoral Acts 2022, as amended, saw a significant increase in disputes caused by party primaries, leading to an unprecedented number of pre-election lawsuits filed in Nigerian courts. These developments highlight the growing importance of court oversight in Nigeria's party politics.

Owoeye et al (2025) opined that intra-party issues were considered outside judicial review because of the belief that the judiciary should limit how it interferes in issues related to the internal workings of political parties. However, the growth of Nigeria's electoral laws has significantly altered this perspective. For example, the Electoral Acts 2022, particularly Section 84, established a clearer process for conducting party primaries, including direct, indirect, and consensus

primaries, and explicitly gave candidates the right to challenge violations of the law in court. This legal inclusion of court jurisdiction highlights the increasing role of courts in party politics, making the judiciary a key player in regulating intra-party democracy in Nigeria (Onapajo & Uzodike, 2014).

Unfortunately, the 2023 general election in Nigeria was marred by challenges such as refusal to align with the party constitution, manipulation of party delegate lists, violence, imposition of candidates, and parallel primaries, despite the amended law's intention to improve internal democracy. These highlighted problems pushed the electoral contest further into the courtroom, with many contestants seeking legal intervention and courts issuing weighty pronouncements with serious implications for aspirants, including party integration, electoral competitiveness, and public confidence in the country's democratic process (Ndubuisi & Omerire, 2025; Erude & Okereka, 2024).

For instance, the validity of section 84(12) faced a significant political and constitutional challenge; the section was considered controversial because it prohibited political appointees from serving as delegates for aspirants. A common experience during the 2023 primary elections was that political officeholders, especially governors, filled the list of party delegates for primary elections with their loyalists. This situation caused most of the primary elections to favor the sitting governors. Unsurprisingly, opposition parties criticized the process, which eventually led to litigation, with the court upholding most of the elections despite evidence of irregularities. According to Ema-Etokudo et al. (2023), this illustrates how judicial intervention can affect the fairness and inclusiveness of party primary elections, with some courts upholding the validity of the provision, while others outright declared it illegal, leading to constitutional uncertainty during the 2023 party primaries.

Yet it highlights the growing importance of the courts in defining what truly constitutes a democratic and constitutionally acceptable primary in Nigeria. It also reveals ambiguities, contradictions, and judicial inconsistencies that need scholarly analysis. Understanding judicial

behavior and decisions, such as how judges reason and whether their rulings promote or hinder inter-party democracy, is crucial for improving Nigeria's electoral democracy. This study aims to assess whether the Nigerian judiciary accurately implements the goals of the Electoral Acts 2022, and whether it balances intervention and deterrence to maintain party independence.

Statement of the problem

Intra-party quagmire, necessitating judicial intervention in politics, marred the 2023 Nigerian general elections. The situation further exposed the deep-seated tensions between the judiciary's constitutional obligations to ensure free and fair contest, and the party's right to manage its internal party affairs. Studies such as Ema-Etokudo et al (2023) noted a series of high-profile and subsequent conflicting decisions, notably the Supreme Court's controversial ruling on the formal Senate President Ahmed Lawan over Bashir Machina as the APC senatorial candidates for Yobe North, and the conflicting Federal High Court rulings over the APC governorship primaries in Akwa-Ibom and Ebonyi state, respectively, created general uncertainty and concern about judicial incursion into purely political matters. The previous events have brought the judiciary into renewed focus, as opinions remain divided on whether the courts are neutral in sensitive pre-election issues. This uncertainty reinforces the pressing need to critically assess the impact of judicial involvement in these selected disputed party primaries in the 2023 Nigerian general elections.

Political party

In contemporary politics, political parties are essential. Their importance cannot be overstated in light of this. Heywood (1997) asserted that political parties are fundamental to the stability of democracy. They are also a group of individuals with common inclinations and attitudes in loyalty to a general political cause, which fundamentally is the pursuit, capture, and retention for as long as democratically viable, of government and its personnel (Agbaje, 1999; Aleyomi, 2013; Nwaigwe, 2019). To have a government in place in

every society, there are bound to be political parties that will contest vigorously to build such a government. It is acknowledged that without political parties, complex modern countries would be impossible to rule. Therefore, parties help with the creation of governments; it also gives governments a level of continuity and uniformity, notably if most of the members of the government are drawn from a single party and therefore united by common affection and attachment (Ugorrji, 2022).

Similarly, political parties are one of the institutions that carry democratic values in any organized society. In this sense, parties must therefore meet certain "institutional guarantees" to effectively fulfill the expectations placed on them; one of such institutional criteria is internal democracy. In another twist, Godwin (2016) remarked that a political party is a 'social group' characterized by a high level of rational steering of behavior toward shared goals, awareness, and expectations. Political parties are significantly distinct from other social groups, such as Labor Unions and other associations, because of the unique roles they serve in the system, including organizing public opinion and serving as agents of political recruitment (Appadorai, 2004; Omodia, 2018).

In essence, political parties are institutional expressions of the struggle for power amongst aggregations of the prevalent political interests in society. They offer a platform for people to actively participate in a nation's political process and for different social interest groups to express their desires. Perhaps, it is the reason one should be able to know what happens between political parties and their internal party mechanism, and how party functionaries and activists connect among themselves within their respective political parties (Suleiman & Gambo, 2024).

Election petition in Nigeria

The Nigerian constitution established the Election Tribunal, which is now part of the federation's Electoral Act Law. More precisely, section 285 (2) of the constitution mandates the establishment of one or more election tribunals, referred to as the Governorship, Legislative, and

Houses Election Tribunals, in each State of the Federation. These courts have exclusive authority and are charged with hearing and rendering decisions on petitions about the legitimacy of elections for the positions of governor, deputy governor, or members of any legislative body. Sections 130–140 of Nigeria's Electoral Act Law (2022), as modified, govern how these tribunals operate.

Section 130(1) of the aforementioned Act states that any challenge to an election or a candidate's return must be made through an election petition that is submitted to the relevant tribunal or court in compliance with the Act or the Constitutional provisions. A formal written request made to a court or other authorized entity is called an election petition. Additionally, a petition submitted in compliance with the Act is referred to by this word. Known as *sui generis*, it is a special and distinctive process with unique features that distinguish it from typical civil or criminal actions. It excludes the parties' civil rights and obligations (Nwanyanwu & Bulodisiye, 2022).

Election Petition Tribunals can be regarded as the trustworthy arena where justice is rendered in situations of elections, given the pertinent laws governing their establishment, special mandate, and operational instructions (Omotola, 2011). Even though electoral petitions have occasionally been brought before tribunals across the country, especially in gubernatorial elections, these cases frequently turn into an intense and acrimonious struggle between politicians who show off their wealth and power.

Election tribunals and the issues of political interference

In Nigeria, election tribunals frequently host high-stakes political contests in which powerful parties fight to gain or hold onto power (Onapajo & Uzodike, 2014). The judicial system may be subjected to excessive political pressure as a result of this phenomenon, endangering its independence. Adeosun (2014) highlighted reports of politicians with significant influence being accused of trying to influence judges' judgments, intimidate witnesses, or obstruct due process to affect the tribunal's procedures. Due to legal disagreements and difficulties

surrounding the 2019 Imo State gubernatorial election, the tribunal had to step in to decide who should have won. The public showed a strong interest in the tribunal's proceedings, and accusations of financial influence, bribery, and political meddling emerged, further undermining confidence in the legal and electoral institutions (Adeibe, 2015; Adom et al, 2024).

For instance, on January 14, 2020, the Supreme Court issued a discordant ruling that designated Senator Hope Uzodinma the incumbent governor of Imo State and removed Rt. Hon. Emeka Ihedioha in controversial circumstances. The 2020 Ondo State gubernatorial election also faced legal challenges and accusations of irregularities, which increased the importance of the tribunal's decisions in settling the disagreements. The influence of financial inducement on the judicial system was questioned, with claims of bribery and corruption undermining the judiciary's objectivity (Nwanyanwu & Bulodisiye, 2022).

The persistent trend of political interference in Nigeria's election tribunals has continued to weaken democracy since 1999. The allegation of judicial capture by political elites is gaining traction and seems to be crucial for their political relevance and survival. Numerous cases confirm that some political elites in Nigeria extend electoral disputes beyond the ballot, turning to the courts to override the popular will of the electorate and undermining democracy (Onapajo & Uzodike, 2014). The examples mentioned are only a few among many in which the powerful in the country boldly cross the line to maintain their hold on power.

Internal democracy

Internal democracy refers to many ways that all party members participate in internal discussions and the decision-making process of their party. Studies have shown that internal democracy is the cornerstone of a democratic system's proper operation. In another way, Aleyomi (2013) noted that a dynamic, functional democracy was created by the logic of party competition rather than internal

democracy. Internal democracy is a top-down, inclusive method of party decision-making that includes primaries, representation, accountability, and equitable conditions for all members to be accepted by the party (Sule & Yahaya, 2019).

Internal democracy, also known as intra-party democracy, refers to a system of mutual decision-making procedures and principles that parties have agreed upon to avoid conflict or manage it to prevent arbitrary decisions or the imposition of candidates against the wishes of the majority of members. For democratic representation and consolidation, internal democracy is essential. It offers space for appropriate member recruitment, responsibility, punishment, and openness. Any party that lacks internal democracy is regarded as undemocratic due to its arbitrary leadership and marginalization of certain members. Even while no political party may declare itself to be undemocratic, the consequences of an absence of internal democracy include anti-party activity, disagreements, electoral defeat, and deviation from democratic norms (Omotola, 2011).

Furthermore, internal democracy includes the selection of candidates by the parties, consultation, internal party discipline and sanction principles, ideology propagation, and accountability. According to Hallberg (2008), advocacy and legal/regulatory actions are the two main strategies for advancing internal democracy. The advocacy viewpoint encompasses peaceful discussion, group decision-making, choosing party leaders, and electing party representatives. The second component is legal and regulatory methods, which should include minority consideration, discussion, party constitutions, gentleman agreements on principles and rules controlling representation, and member discipline (Owoeye et al, 2025).

The process of integrating broader democratic ideals with the means of establishing party politics and discipline within political parties can also be categorized under the concept of internal democracy. It serves as a channel through which political parties promote open methods of nominations or primaries, members' ideological foundations, and uphold law and order (Greenfeld, 2012; Jinadu, 2011). The basic

principles of democracy are expressed within political parties through internal democracy. The core idea of internal democracy is that all party members should have access to transparency, accountability, and fair play, ensuring equal opportunity. Intra-party conflicts are a major issue that arises when internal democracy is lacking and can violate democratic principles. Nigerian political parties and democracy have experienced intra-party strife since the First Republic (1960–1966). However, these conflicts became more noticeable during the Fourth Republic (1999–Present), possibly due to the longest period of democratization in the country's history. Intra-party conflicts have various effects on Nigerian political parties and democratization, including cross-carpeting, violence, anti-party activities, instability, poor governance, and other obstacles to proper democratization.

The former ruling People's Democratic Party (PDP), which has dominated Nigeria continuously for sixteen years (1999–2015), was based on two main issues: intra-party strife and a lack of internal democracy. It was the reason the opposition All Progressives Congress (APC) was able to defeat the PDP in the 2015 general election. However, less than two years into its rule, the APC found itself embroiled in a variety of intra-party issues, including internal division within the state, an executive-legislative battle in an intra-party show, and internal contention among party executives.

Intra-party politics and democracy in Nigeria

The democratic ethos is inextricably linked to factors like competition, political negotiation, and compromise. The political party is the means by which it becomes a reality. The situation of intra-party democracy and/or internal politics has become extremely concerning in the Nigerian political space. The traditional method of operation has various implications, such as the aggressive nature of intra-party operations, which often leads to violent altercations and the loss of lives and property. Nigeria has continuously performed poorly in some previous general elections due to the issue of intra-party activities and disputes within the party. In the run-up to the 2015 general election, the opposition parties and the ruling Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP)

created a dynasty of persistent intra-party violence and animosity, with no discipline or regard for the party's ideals (Mbomdemyi & Ambani, 2012; Ugorrji, 2022).

A tragic event in Nigeria's democratic journey is the division brought about by the absence of democracy within the parties from the beginning of the Fourth Republic, which started in 1999. These conflicts take many different forms, such as the vicious rivalry between so-called "godfathers" and their "godsons," the brutal murders of candidates, violent altercations, snatching ballot boxes, kidnapping, assault, and never-ending court cases that result in the disastrous cancellation and annulment of previous electoral victories. Due to the imposition of candidates and the domineering behavior of party leaders, there have been instances of internal party crises that have resulted in violence.

The strained relationship between President Goodluck Jonathan and former President Olusegun Obasanjo, 2010 to 2015, is one of the most severe examples in recent history. The latter imposed Goodluck Jonathan on the party. The party primaries held on 10 December 2010 resulted in party acrimony and internal wrangling. His victory in the presidential election as an Ijaw man from a minority region did not receive popular party support. However, strong resistance within the party caused the music to change in the following election year (2015). To express their displeasure with the perhaps imposed nominee, there was a gale of defection in the party, including five sitting governors, and other prominent members from the national assembly Adibe, 2015)

Apart from the foregoing, other gross violations of internal party mechanisms were recorded within the period. The leading political party, i.e., the People's Democratic Party (PDP), was seen to have little or no regard for party constitution and internal democracy. The general elections of that period left a lot to be desired; the party primaries were laced with irregularities, utter imposition of candidates, and *godfatherism* became so popularized to the extent that the party lost out to the opposition in the 2015 general elections due to an internal crisis.

Theoretical exposition: The Separation of Powers Theory (SPT)

Authors like Kmiec (2004) have claimed that the separation of powers emphasizes the need for each part of government to fulfill its own specific duties. Legislative, executive, and judicial are the three branches of government in this context, and the institutions created to perform these functions are bound by the fundamental rule that no person or entity should exercise more than one of these powers. However, Singh (1996) contends that true separation of powers is impossible in practice re-emphasized that the complete division of powers and the structures and operations of government have never been fully achieved and are not practically acceptable. Concerning the division of power among the three branches of government, it is one thing to endorse and articulate a basic rule that categorizes and allocates powers in this manner, and quite another to address the practical challenges of defining the powers of each branch and the political implications of rigidly adhering to these boundaries (O'Regan, 2005).

The notion of checks and balances, according to Labuschagne (2004), whereby each branch of government is given unique powers intended to keep a check on the execution of other branches' duties, is the most fundamental aspect of the separation of powers doctrine. This makes sure that neither the rule of law nor the welfare of the populace is compromised as a result of the government's branches exceeding their authority. Some critics, like Mbodenyi and Ambani (2012), suggested that it permits some interference within the government.

In an ideal situation, O'Regan (2005) opined that the legislative branch checks the executive by keeping the power to remove the president when the occupier stoops to the arbitrary use of power; in the same vein, the executive checks the legislature by giving a measure the president's consent to make it law. The court uses its power of review to hold the executive and legislature accountable. In contrast, by choosing who will serve on the judiciary, the government and legislature control the judiciary through appointment and financial allocation. Unfortunately, the executive often utilizes this gap to usurp the powers of the judiciary, thereby undermining their constitutional right.

The main idea behind the doctrine of separation of powers is that power abuse will result from a concentration of too much power in one person or institution. It can, however, be argued that instances of over-concentration of power in a particular arm of government (executive), or in a person, are well pronounced in Nigeria and Africa in general. The nature of “Super-Presidentialism” operational in Nigeria has greatly offended the doctrine of separation of powers. The 1999 constitution gave enormous functions to the executive arm to be performed. For example, the Constitution of 1999 empowers the president and governors to hire and fire members of the judiciary. This has made the Nigerian judiciary's survival at the mercy of the executive.

The foregoing was re-echoed by Greenfield (2012), who laments that the three traditional branches of government, executive, legislative, and judicial, were established under the Constitution. But the Baron Montesque arrangement was, however, uneven, in a political system where the executive branch, more especially, the presidency had greater authority than the other branches. The dramatic and forceful removal of the Nigerian Chief Justice (Walter Onnoghen) from office in 2019 on the eve of the general elections by the powerful executive headed by the president attests to this claim. A similar circumstance played out at the sub-national government level of Kogi State, where former governor Yahaya Bello made life difficult for former Chief Judge of the State, Nasir Ajanah, due to abuse of power that eventually saw to the untimely exit of the jurist in 2020.

In Nigeria, Masinde (2019) contends that the judiciary has come to be seen as the executive branch's underling, a defender of state power, and a weak defender of citizens' rights. It didn't help that the nation had endured a protracted period of military dictatorship during which an authoritarian regime governed it. The military nature of the exercise of power that saw to the subjugation, which made other branches of the government bow to his will, is not expected to be seen in a democracy where the rule of law is the standard.

Although the 1999 constitution gave the judiciary considerable formal autonomy, it was nonetheless operated like a government agency rather

than as an equal and autonomous branch of government (Alabi, 2008). As a result, the court lost its institutional independence and turned into the executive's scullery maid. The executive seems to have launched a constitutional assault against the judiciary in practical terms. The executive's overbearing dominance undermined the court, and it was especially unwilling to carry out its normal task of safeguarding and upholding the fundamental principle of separation of powers (Singh, 1996). In contrast, the American Constitution acknowledges its significance, stating that the executive authority is vested in the President, the legislative power is vested in Congress, and the judicial power is vested in the Supreme Court.

Empirical case evaluation

Nigeria's electoral jurisprudence may continue to be plagued by judicial technicalities. Those who believed that the justices would uphold the sanctity of section 115(d) of the Electoral Act, which prohibits a person from signing a nomination paper or running for office in more than one constituency at the same election, are disappointed by the Supreme Court's decision to confirm Senate President Dr. Ahmad Lawan as the All Progressive Congress Senatorial Candidate for the Yobe North. For many Nigerians, it was a stunning moment.

In the majority ruling, the Apex court also overturned the Abuja Court of Appeal's ruling, which had upheld the trial court's decision in designating Bashir Machina as Yobe North's senatorial candidate. Machina claimed that the All Progressive Congress (APC) had falsely replaced his name with Lawan's. An original summons should not be used where there is a fraudulent allegation. To substantiate claims of fraud, witnesses had to be called. However, the Apex court ruled in a majority ruling by Justices Emmanuel Agim and Adamu Jauro that Lawan never took part in the May 28 APC primary because he voluntarily withdrew to run in the June 8, 2022, presidential primary.

Machina was controversially denied justice by the Supreme Court on technicality ground. It is perplexing because the same Supreme Court judges frequently employ technicalities to deny plaintiffs justice,

despite the Supreme Court's warning to subordinate courts against doing so. The use of technicalities to deny Machina justice was argued to be wholly unjust. The *Bashir Machina v. Ahmad Lawan* case will also continue to haunt the Supreme Court and Nigeria's electoral jurisprudence for a very long time, just as Justice Nweze stated in his dissenting opinion when the same Supreme Court heard a case involving Senator Hope Uzodinma and a former governor, Hon. Emeka Ihedioha. The apex court on the party primary has further reinforced executive overbearing influence on the judiciary, and eroded public confidence in the judiciary.

In a related development, Godswill Akpabio, a former governor of Akwa Ibom State and minister of Niger Delta Affairs, ran in the All Progressives Congress (APC) presidential primary ahead of the 2023 general elections. He then applied for and was granted the APC senatorial ticket for the Akwa Ibom North-West District at the same time. His action was greeted with legal disputes and general condemnation.

By prohibiting a single candidate from running for more than one post within a single election cycle, this rule aims to increase justice, lessen electoral manipulation, and guarantee representation. In a unanimous ruling on February 3, 2023, the Supreme Court upheld Akpabio as the APC candidate for the Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District (Appeal Nos. SC/CV/1459/2022 & SC/CV/1539/2022). The decision revoked the previous Court of Appeal ruling that Udom Ekpoudomas was the legitimate candidate, decided that the nomination of a candidate was an internal political party matter that fell outside the purview of normal courts, and gave the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) instructions to acknowledge Akpabio as the rightful candidate of the party

Given the facts, this decision clearly violates Section 115(d) of the Electoral Act 2022 as amended; Akpabio took part in the APC presidential primary, which is a formal procedure that includes media coverage, nomination forms, and voting. Later on in the same election cycle, he received a Senate nomination. The Electoral Act states that

this should be a crime that carries a jail sentence rather than something that is up to the parties to decide. This inconsistency calls into question the independence and consistency of court rulings in upholding electoral rules, undermining the legitimacy of Nigeria's electoral process.

Conclusion/recommendation

The cases listed all highlight a troubling trend in Nigeria's Fourth Republic: the judiciary is increasingly affecting political outcomes, often in ways that seem to undermine legal accountability and promote elite manipulation of the democratic process. This raises questions about the integrity of electoral institutions, the rule of law, and the country's prospects for democratic consolidation. The recent emphasis by the Supreme Court on procedural details in cases like *Lawan v. Machina* underscores the urgent need for clearer procedural rules in election-related disputes. Frequent disputes over whether to initiate cases with originating summonses or writs of summons contribute to inconsistent decisions based on form rather than substance. To address this, the National Judicial Council (NJC), the Rules of Court Committees, and other relevant legal bodies should review and clarify the procedural framework governing pre-election and post-election matters.

More importantly, Nigerian electoral jurisprudence should undergo a paradigm change so that election petitions are judged based on substantial justice rather than technicalities. Rather than dismissing petitions for small procedural flaws or errors, courts should give priority to the will of the electorate and the just resolution of disputes. This strategy is in line with a long-standing legal rule that election petitions should be evaluated on their merits. These support the demand for revisions to guarantee that *Lawan v. Machina* and similar cases are resolved based on the genuine purpose of the electorate and the parties' substantive rights rather than on limited technical grounds. Both the legitimacy of election adjudication and public trust in Nigeria's democratic process will be improved by more precise procedural rules and a judicial dedication to substantive justice.

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